

Analysis of temperature profiles in flooded rice field: preliminary results

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The Po Valley is one of the uppermost northern areas in the Boreal hemisphere for rice. At these extreme latitudes, water submerging the rice field significantly affects meteorological variables. In particular, water affects soil and canopy temperature by smoothing the differences between thermal extremes (Fig. 1). Cold shocks or strong changes between day and night temperatures can negatively affect rice cycle and production, particularly when they occur during emergence and at the preflowering phase. For this reason, European rice growers traditionally consider water level as the most important factor during these phases. Few studies have been carried out to improve knowledge on water influences on canopy temperature. Rice growth and development models

used to simulate the behavior of the rice crop require only air temperature as a daily input, whereas the meristematic apex and global plant behavior depend on water temperature, at least up to the stem elongation phase.

This note presents (1) some preliminary results of a modeling process that describes a temperature profile (soil, water, canopy, air) in a rice field during a period in which the field was not completely covered by the canopy by using temperature data collected in a standard weather station in 1989-91, and (2) a description of a method used to collect data after the closed canopy stage in 2002. In temperate (mid-latitude) rice areas, the proposed model could be used to predict crop phenological stages strongly influenced by water temperatures

(Confalonieri et al 2001). Moreover, water temperature influences the life cycles of all the species living in rice fields. For example, the mortality and development of the aquatic stages of mosquito species (*Aedes*, *Culex*, *Anopheles*, etc.) are strongly influenced by surface water temperature, which determines the number of emerging adults (Jetten and Takken 1994, Lucassen 1996).

Data collected from Rosate (Milan Province, Italy) in three seasons (1989, 1990, 1991) at a standard agrometeorological station (Bocchi 1992) were used for modeling. Data on air temperature at 1.5 m above the soil surface, temperature of water in contact with the soil, global solar radiation, and albedo were obtained. At present, the course of water temperature between sowing and the "closed canopy" stage (when the canopy completely covers the water-soil) is modeled using two different approaches: empirical and mechanistic. The empirical model simulates temperature in the bottom of the water profile as a function of air temperature of the last 5 d. The mechanistic approach simulates hourly values of surface water temperature by solving the equation of surface energy balance.

The comparison between measured and simulated data using the empirical model is shown in the table. The fitting indices were those proposed by Loague and Green (1991): the relative root mean squared error (RRMSE, 0–100%, optimum = 0%), the coeffi

Fig. 1. Daily data showing water smoothing effects on temperature during the crop cycle (data collected in Rosate, Italy, in 1989).

Indices of agreement between observed and simulated values. TwB is the water temperature measured at the soil-water interface.

Parameter	RMSE	EF	CRM	CD	Slope	Intercept	R ²
TwB Min (empirical model)	6.68	0.71	0.03	0.93	0.87	2.63	0.78
TwB Max (empirical model)	4.02	0.81	0.01	0.81	0.84	3.86	0.85
TwB Min (mechanistic model)	12.35	0.56	-0.02	1.48	0.93	0.95	0.58

coefficient of determination (CD, 0–1, optimum = 1, which indicates whether the model reproduces the trend of measured values or not), the modeling efficiency (EF, $-\infty \leq EF \leq +\infty$, optimum = 1; if positive, the model is a better predictor than the average of measured values), the coefficient of residual mass (CRM, 0–1, optimum = 0; a positive sign indicates model underestimation), and the parameters of the regression equation between observed and predicted values. The low values of RRMSE and the values of CD close to 1 show that the model is quite accurate. The table also shows some preliminary simulation results of the mechanistic model. The fitting indices indicate that the model is able to simulate the processes in a rice field and encourage the future activities of development, calibration, and validation.

To model the temperature profile in the period after the “closed canopy” stage, data collected inside (at different heights) and over the canopy layer are required. Thus, we built a floating structure (Fig. 2) with stems holding thermometers in the canopy (at 20 and 60 cm from the water surface), on the water surface, in the bottom of the rice field, and over the canopy (at 150 cm from the water surface). The structure is so light that it is able to float and maintain the system undisturbed near sensors. The structure can float in very shallow water bodies (about 4–5 cm deep), is able to follow the water level, and can be used for studies

on weed management, fertilizing strategies, and crop development. The structure is made of aluminum pipe connected by aluminum or plastic hand-made structures. The floats are little slabs of polyurethane. Temperature data loggers (external sensor; 12-bit version) are located inside radiation screens (Micros Technologies). Figure 3 shows some results.

References

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Fig. 2. The floating station (details are in the text).

Fig. 3. Temperature measured at different levels with the floating station (Vignate [MI]; 48 h starting from 1 Jun 2002, 0600) at the soil-water interface, on the surface, and at 150 cm from the water surface. The effect of flooding on water temperature is evident on the second day, when water produces a significant delay in the afternoon temperature decrease.